

Special Relativity's Light-Signal Mediated Definition of Synchronism is Without Contradictions Only in Phase Space When Considering the Quantum Behavior of Light

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Abstract

Einstein's 1905 derivation of Special Relativity is revisited, showing that its definition of synchronism (using light-mediated signaling among clocks) is without contradictions only in phase space – not in configuration space – when the quantum behavior of light is considered. The result is a method of description of mechanics in phase space which is characterized by spatio-temporal probability density distributions and discrete spectra for conserved quantities, with results that parallel those of Schrodinger's canonical formulation of quantum mechanics, but achieved without use of the de Broglie matter-wave hypothesis or its mathematical artifacts (wavefunction, Hilbert space). The descriptive method is developed and then applied to pedagogical systems, such as the particle-in-a-box, bouncing ball and harmonic oscillator, with results then compared to the canonical quantum descriptions of those systems.

1 Introduction

The derivation of special relativity hinges in part on a definition of synchronism that involves sending light signals among spatially separated clocks, exploiting the invariant velocity of light to ensure that this definition is "... *free from contradictions*"[2]. That approach uses an abstraction of light (as a "signal" or "ray") which is presumed to be valid for sending signals between clocks with spatial separation of arbitrary resolution (assuming the possibility of arbitrarily small clocks), and is agnostic about the chromatic composition of the light. This classical, abstracted model of light does indeed facilitate a definition of synchronism that is free from contradictions of the kind Einstein laid out in his paper.

[8] But if we consider a simple (least complex) form of light signal, while accounting for the quantum behavior of light¹ (with that light signal² being an ensemble of identically prepared photons which are monochromatic, phase-coherent and identically polarized – i.e. with identical elliptical eccentricity, elliptical orientation and chirality) and its inevitably probabilistic model of photon detection – and thus light signal detection – it is evident that this method of signaling yields, at a given configuration space location (of arbitrary resolution), **differing** values of the probability density of signal reception/detection, depending on the wavelength of light employed, rather than the single-valued certainty of detection which the classical, abstracted model of light yields. This is illustrated in the following plots, showing how different probability density values (density indicated by curve height on vertical axis and equivalently by colored shading) are obtained at a given configuration space location x on the horizontal axis (e.g., at location $x = 0.5$) for light of (a) longer wavelength, and (b) shorter wavelength:

(a)

(b)

And because there is no obvious justification for preference of one wavelength over another for use in signaling, this results in a definition of synchronism which, in configuration space, is **not**

¹ i.e. Einstein's photoelectric model and Born's [3] probabilistic interpretation of light wave intensity.

² Hereafter we will refer to this kind of light as "signal-light."

free from contradictions – that is, two light signals of different wavelengths, in general, yield mutually contradictory probability densities of reception/detection at a given point in configuration space. If we assume that a synchronization scheme must be independent of wavelength in order to be universally applicable, then we can see that although the invariant velocity of light is clearly necessary for clock synchronization without contradiction for some degrees of spatial resolution, this property alone is not sufficient for consistent (i.e. without contradictions) clock synchronization with arbitrary spatial resolution.

Although we see that the spatial distribution of the probability density of detection in configuration space is contingent on the wavelength of the light used for signaling, and that this contingency is awkward to express in configuration space, nevertheless the awkwardness of expression vanishes when we describe synchronization in phase space, employing the Planck–Einstein quantum model of light³. When considered this way – where a photon’s wavelength and frequency are related to its momentum and energy by Planck’s constant – the propagation of the synchronization signal becomes simply described as going from one phase space coordinate to another (as will be shown), resulting in the establishment of a scalar field in phase space, which indicates the probability density of a clock at a given phase space location being synchronized.

And thus, when employing a quantum light signal for clock synchronization – of the simple form suggested above – in phase space, we do obtain a definition of synchronism that is fully free from contradictions and correct for spatial separation of arbitrary resolution, as every location in phase space has a **single** value of the probability density of reception/detection of the synchronization signal. In cases where the resolution of spatial separation is substantially larger than the wavelength of light signals used for synchronization, we recover the classical limit of the light ray/signal abstraction originally employed, even for monochromatic light. This single-valued characteristic is illustrated in the following phase space plot (the derivation of which will be presented in section 3 of this paper) where probability density of photon detection is indicated by colored shading, with horizontal axis representing spatial displacement x and vertical axis representing corresponding momentum p_x :

³ Relating light’s wavelength/frequency to its momentum/energy

With the necessity now established of defining the clock synchronization process in phase space in order to have a definition of synchronism that is fully free from contradictions, we next examine the consequences of the result of such a process for some aspects of the description of mechanics.

It is worth noting the parallel between the approach developed in this paper and Einstein's 1905 derivation of special relativity: just as the invariant velocity of light imposes configuration space constraints that affect the definition of simultaneity and resolve inconsistencies in classical electrodynamics, so too does the invariant action of light—embodied in its wave and photon nature—impose phase space constraints that affect measurability and facilitate a blending of classical dynamics with quantum statistical behavior. The scalar field introduced here embodies these constraints, encoding the probability of measurement with a synchronized clock, and yields, when combined with the probability of presence along classical trajectories, quantum-like probability densities without invoking de Broglie waves or their mathematical realization as wavefunctions and operator formalism, and arguably avoiding their metaphysical problems. The resulting framework offers an operational, light-constrained reformulation of mechanics that is physically grounded and free from contradictions.

Although this paper will focus on the novel consequences of this (quantum) light-mediated clock synchronization considered in phase space (and, subsequently, in configuration space), rather than on the well-known consequences of (abstracted) light-mediated clock synchronization in configuration space first presented in Einstein's 1905 Relativity paper, we assume these two sets of consequences can be subsequently integrated into a coherent description of mechanics at relativistic velocities ($\sim c$) and at quantum resolutions of action ($\sim \hbar$) in phase space.

1.1 Conventions and Assumptions Employed in this Paper

Throughout this paper, the broad assumption is made that the probability density of presence along a dimension of linear/radial/angular displacement is proportional to the reciprocal of the velocity along that displacement (i.e. proportional to “dwell time”), with the awareness that there may be other, more proper ways of quantifying probability density of presence. It is assumed that proper normalization of probability density of presence would not substantially change the results of the model presented in this paper.

We assume the Born-Einstein interpretation of the quantum behavior of light because of its embodiment of some essential quantum properties of light (light quanta, probability density distribution, etc.)

In the discussion that follows, we will make use of a notational simplification for trigonometric functions, the purpose and details of which are explained in appendix A.

Other conventions are noted in appendix B.

The canonical quantum mechanical model referenced throughout the paper is that presented in standard treatments, such as Liboff [4].

Executable models of the various mathematical formulations presented in this paper are available in the form of Mathematica[®] scripts.

2 Paper Organization

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 3 examines and refines the clock synchronization process of special relativity. Section 4 examines the consequences of the refined clock synchronization process for the description of mechanics in phase space. Section 5 develops and applies a method of description for the mechanics of bound systems with a selection of single-term polynomial potentials. Section 6 applies the results of section 5 to representative bound systems.

3 Clock Synchronization⁴

This section examines the clock synchronization process in phase space, and examines the scalar field of measurability that arises from that process.

⁴ In this paper, we apply our refinement of the clock synchronization process only to clocks *within* a given inertial reference frame. It is expected that the same refinement can be applied more generally to clock synchronization *among* inertial reference frames, and that the consequent descriptions of mechanics will apply to systems involving relativistic velocities.

3.1 Synchronizing Clocks in Phase Space

We will refer to the process of clock synchronization employed in the original formulation of special relativity [1]. We examine this process in phase space so as to take into account the spatial variation of light ray detection probability density, as described above. Specifically, the operational definition of simultaneity laid out in section §1 of that formulation, where it is stated that “ ... *We assume that this definition of synchronism is ... possible for any number of points ...*,” [5] (taking “any number of points” to include “all points”), is modified to state that the definition of synchronism permits only the *probability density* of clock synchronization at any point, in accord with the Born–Einstein interpretation of light amplitude cited above.

The spatial variation of the probability density P of detecting a photon of a light ray of wavelength λ is expressed in the Born–Einstein relation as the square of the amplitude of the electric field ε of an electromagnetic wave.

For simplicity, we first examine the modified process of clock synchronization and its consequences in 1-dimensional configuration space (and thus in the corresponding 2-dimensional phase space).

Starting with the classical equation describing the variation in amplitude ε of the electric field for a light wave of wavelength λ propagating in the positive x direction:

$$\varepsilon = \cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(x - ct)\right]$$

The Born–Einstein relation therefore amounts to:

$$P = \varepsilon^2 = \cos^2\left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(x - ct)\right] \quad (1)$$

This expresses the probability density, $0 \leq P \leq 1$, of detecting a photon of wavelength λ at location x and time t in configuration space, in a given inertial reference frame.

Employing the Planck–Einstein relations for the momentum $p_A = \frac{h}{\lambda}$ and energy $E_A = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$ of a light quantum, we can consider a light ray of wavelength λ propagating from point $A(x_A, t_A)$ to point $B(x_B, t_B)$ in configuration space to be equivalent to a light ray propagating from point $A(x_A, t_A, p_A, E_A)$ to point $B(x_B, t_B, p_B, E_B)$ in phase space. Therefore, the probability density P of detecting the light ray, in terms of phase space coordinates, is equivalently expressed as follows:

$$P = \cos^2\left[\frac{xp_x - tE}{h}\right] \quad (2)$$

This expresses the probability density of detecting a photon at location (x, t, p_x, E) in phase space. This is taken, consequently, to express the probability density of a clock at that location in phase space being synchronized.

This relation can be thought of as defining a scalar⁵ field in phase space, the value of which is the **probability density of a clock at each location (x, t, p_x, E) in phase space being synchronized** (elsewhere in this paper, we will refer to this as the “scalar field of measurability”). This scalar field is denoted by \mathcal{P} :

$$\mathcal{P} = \cos^2\left[\frac{xp_x - tE}{\hbar} - \Phi\right] \quad (3)$$

Measurement with a clock that is not synchronized makes the time of the measurement indeterminate, and thus any velocity (thus momentum) assessment from that time indeterminate.

This scalar field can be visualized in the following plots of \mathcal{P} in phase space ($\Phi = 0, \frac{\pi}{2}$). The momentum p_x is on the vertical axis, and the spatial displacement x is on the horizontal axis. In the top set of plots, \mathcal{P} is represented by shades of blue, with blue indicating $\mathcal{P} = 1$, white indicating $\mathcal{P} = 0$, and shades of blue indicating $(0 < \mathcal{P} < 1)$. In the bottom set of plots, \mathcal{P} is represented by surface height.

⁵ Could this be thought of as more than just a scalar field of probability density of detection, and in fact additionally as a vector field of probability density of orientation/polarization (of E field) in either of two opposite directions, or no direction at all at nodes, and thus possibly as a basis for intrinsic spin?

$$\mathcal{P} = \cos^2 \left[\frac{xp_x - tE}{\hbar} \right]$$

$$\mathcal{P} = \cos^2 \left[\frac{xp_x - tE}{\hbar} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right]$$

Note that the value \mathcal{P} tells us only the probability density of the clock at the phase space location (x, p_x, t, E) being synchronized. It says nothing, of course, about the presence or absence of something to measure at that location—e.g., a particle with momentum p_x and energy E at the configuration space location (x, t) .

In contrast, the original clock synchronization scheme of special relativity implicitly defines this scalar field as having a uniform value of 1 for all points in phase space:

$$\mathcal{P} = 1$$

which is, in terms of the phase space probability density defined above:

$$\mathcal{P} = \sin^2 \left[\frac{xp_x - tE}{\hbar} \right] + \cos^2 \left[\frac{xp_x - tE}{\hbar} \right]$$

We might view this constraint on measurability in phase space as analogous to the constraint on clock synchronization in configuration space — which is a consequence of the finite, invariant velocity of light — permitting only causally accessible clocks (namely, those within the light cone of an event in 4-space) to be synchronized. Similarly, in phase space, only causally accessible clocks — meaning those within the light cone **and** in proportion to the probability density of light signal detection⁶ — can be synchronized. The scalar field can be visualized within the light cone of an event at the origin as (for increasing phase space plane areas):

⁶ Do iso-contours of the scalar field in phase space (x, p_x) play a role analogous to that of a light cone in configuration space (x, t) ?

In the following plots of the scalar field, it can be seen how the classical relativity concept of uniform causal accessibility within the light cone (resulting from the abstracted concept of light signals) emerges from the scalar field for increasing phase plane area (in units of action, corresponding to higher values of the conserved quantity spectral index):

Regarding the canonical quantum notion of particle presence being contingent on the measurement of that particle's presence⁷: it can be argued that particles are no less present due to mere **probable** ($0 \leq P \leq 1$) availability of a synchronized clock at a given point on their trajectory in the scalar field than they are less present due to **certain** ($P = 0$) unavailability of a synchronized clock outside an event's light cone. In either case, a synchronized clock is unavailable due to effective causal inaccessibility, and so [consistent] measurement of something present at that location is not possible.

To summarize, the original clock synchronization process is refined by taking into account the Planck–Einstein quantum model of light and the Born–Einstein interpretation of light intensity with the result being the definition/establishment of a scalar field in phase space, which indicates the probability of a clock at each phase space location being synchronized. We next examine the consequences of this for the description of mechanics.

3.2 Extending Light's Constraints to Phase Space

The clock synchronization method put forth in the derivation of special relativity – combined with the method described above – suggests that the fundamental invariants of light impose two complementary operational constraints on the structure of physical reality, one in configuration

⁷ That is, perhaps measurement **effecting** presence.

space and one in phase space. In special relativity, the invariant velocity c of light structures spacetime through its constraint on the relationship between space and time in configuration space, limiting causal accessibility from a given event to all events on or within its light cone, thereby defining the permissible causal structure of classical kinematics.

As a parallel, the invariant action h of light structures phase space through its constraint on the relationship between spacetime and momentum-energy in phase space, limiting measurability in the form of the scalar field of measurability. In this framework, light's quantum behavior modulates the probability density of detecting particles⁸ along classical phase space trajectories, producing a field whose iso-contours represent regions of identical measurability. These phase space iso-contours might be viewed as the phase space counterparts of light cones in configuration space: they embody the phase space periodicity of measurability, modulated by the scale \hbar .

As a result, the causal organization of events in spacetime and the measurability of trajectories in phase space both originate from fundamental properties of light — c and h respectively. Together, they can be seen as defining dual operational structures: one governing motion and causal influence, and the other governing measurement and detectability. This parallel suggests that light not only constrains the kinematics of spacetime but also fundamentally sculpts the probabilistic structure of phase space, arguably establishing a deeper operational unity between classical and quantum descriptions.

4 Descriptions in Phase Space

We will now examine how to describe the mechanics of a system using the constellation of synchronized clocks in phase space, as established by the process detailed above. Because there is only a probability of a clock at a given location in phase space being synchronized, there is consequently only a probability of measuring the presence of a physical body at that location using such a synchronized clock. The descriptions will consist of the spectral values of conserved quantities (e.g., energy, angular momentum, spatial orientation of angular momentum, etc.) and spatial probability density distributions. More work is required to describe expectation values for observables, the uncertainty principle (as it applies to non-commuting observables), complete sets of commuting observables, and other aspects of the quantum description of mechanics.

⁸ In this model, the probability of detecting a particle and the probability of establishing a synchronized clock at a given location might be considered operationally equivalent, with both determined by the scalar field of measurability shaped by light's quantum properties.

4.0 Simplification: Ignoring tE Phase Term and Using Only 2 Dimensional Phase Space

For simplicity, we initially consider only systems within the portion of a reference frame where clock synchronization has already taken place (allowing us to ignore the $\frac{tE}{\hbar}$ phase term in the expression for P_m).

Additionally, we will examine systems—for now—only in 2-dimensional phase space, ignoring the time dimension (tE) of phase space for a 1-dimensional configuration space—although the concept of a 3-dimensional phase space that includes the time dimension (tE) is illustrated in plot (e) in the following section (4.1). For bound systems, the energy is a constant of the motion, and so it is only a constant scaling multiplier for the time axis of 3-dimensional phase space.

It remains to be seen whether the longer trajectory in 3-dimensional phase space will yield better alignment between the probability density distribution nodes for this model and the corresponding results for the canonical model.

4.1 Probability Density of Measurability

If, when measuring the positions of a particle in motion along its phase space trajectory, we consider only measurements at those positions where there is a synchronized clock, then our description of the particle's motion will consist, in part, of the values of \mathcal{P} at all points along the particle's trajectory. We will refer to the value of \mathcal{P} at each point along the particle's phase space trajectory as the **probability density of measurability** along that trajectory, denoted by $P_m(\alpha)$, where α is the angle between the radius (from the phase space origin to a point on the particle's phase space trajectory) and the positive spatial displacement (x) axis.

Using the potential $V(x) = Kx^2$ as an example, **plot (a)** illustrates the 2D phase space trajectory (for a specific energy) through the scalar field (green circle, with probability \mathcal{P} depicted as density indicated by shading); **plot (b)** illustrates the same concept as plot (a) but with probability \mathcal{P} depicted as surface height and probability along trajectory (red) as the green curve; **plot (c)** depicts the same as **plot (b)**, but shows only the scalar field on and within the phase space trajectory in order to clarify the shape of the probability density curve along the trajectory; **plot (d)** depicts the value of the scalar field (on the vertical axis) only along the phase space trajectory in blue, and shows its parallel projection onto configuration space (the plane $p_x = 0$) in red; **plot (e)** illustrates the probability density of measurability $P_m(\alpha)$ — for an assortment of energies, corresponding to an assortment of trajectory diameters (the effect of which energies on the behavior of $P_m(\alpha)$ will be examined in the later section on “Behavior of P_m in Phase Space”) — along that phase space trajectory on the vertical axis; and finally **plot (f)** illustrates the helical trajectory in a 3 dimensional phase space that includes a time coordinate

(where the vertical axis depicts time t , and P_m is the vertical displacement above the trajectory curve):

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

From these plots, it can be seen how the probability density of measurability along the particle's phase space trajectory emerges as the intersection of the particle's phase trajectory and the scalar field of measurability.

Note the similarity of the projection of the probability density of measurability along the particle's phase space trajectory (onto the plane $p = 0$) to the projection of the Wigner quasiprobability density (onto the same plane). But recognize that the model proposed in this paper involves a *classical* (not quantum) phase space in which is defined the scalar field of measurability, which modulates the measurability of the particle along its *classical* phase space trajectory. This is illustrated in the following phase space illustrative plots with this model depicted in (a) $n = 0$, (b) $n = 1$, (c) $n = 19$, and (d) depicting the equivalent Wigner function phase space representations:

(a) (b)

(c)

(d)

Deviation from the Wigner function in these plots (i.e. maxima conforming to the shape of a classical probability density plot) is remedied in section 4.2 when we introduce the probability density of presence along the classical trajectory.

4.1.1 Classical Limit

It can be seen how the classical model emerges out of this model when the scalar field is examined along the phase space trajectory for systems with increasing energies (spectral index values) or, alternatively, a decreasing value of \hbar . This is depicted in the following plots, where the probability density of measurability along the phase space trajectory approaches unity (solid blue curve). Distortions in the scalar field seen for $n=80, 160$ are Moiré patterns resulting from distortions due to insufficient resolution in the plot. As with the plots above, the following illustrative plots are for the potential $V(x) = Kx^2$.

4.1.2 Measurement in Classical Physics

If the concept of measurement in classical physics could plausibly be defined (for simplicity, we will here consider only one spatial dimension and its corresponding momentum) as the "detection of a particle at position (p_x, x, E, t) in phase space" or, equivalently, the "detection of a particle of momentum p_x and energy E at position (x, t) in configuration space", then the concept of measurement in the model presented in this paper modifies that classical concept only by assigning a probability density of the availability of a synchronized clock at position (p_x, x, E, t) in phase space with which to record the detection of a particle at that point.

With this definition in hand, **measurability** is more precisely defined as the availability of a synchronized clock at a phase space position with which to record the detection of a particle at that phase space location.

4.2 Probability Density of Presence

Independent of the value of $P_m(\alpha)$ at a given location on a particle's phase space trajectory, there is also the probability density of the particle **being present** at that location on the trajectory. We will refer to this probability density as the particle's **probability density of presence of the particle**, denoted by $P_p(\alpha)$. The probability density of a particle's presence, generally inversely proportional to its velocity, is a function of the position-dependent potential influencing the particle's velocity.

Using the same $V(x) = Kx^2$ example potential, we see illustrated in plot (a) the probability density of presence $P_p(\alpha)$ along the phase space trajectory. To help visualize the shape of $P_p(\alpha)$, plot (b) shows the parallel projection of $P_p(\alpha)$ onto the plane $p(\alpha) = 0$:

(a)

(b)

4.3 Probability Density of Measurable Presence

Taking into account the probability densities of measurability and presence at each point along a particle's phase space trajectory, we define the probability density of measuring a particle with momentum p_x and energy E using a synchronized clock at location (x, t, p_x, E) in phase space as being the combination (i.e., algebraic product) of the probability density of the particle's presence P_p at that location and the probability density of measurability P_m at that location. This resulting **probability density of measurable presence** is denoted by P_{mp} and defined simply as follows:

$$P_{mp} = P_p \cdot P_m$$

Using the same $V(x) = Kx^2$ example potential as above, we see illustrated in plot (a) both the probability density of measurable presence $P_{mp}(\alpha)$ and the probability density of presence $P_p(\alpha)$ along the phase space trajectory. To help visualize how the shapes of $P_{mp}(\alpha)$ and $P_p(\alpha)$ are related, plot (b) illustrates the parallel projection of both $P_{mp}(\alpha)$ and $P_p(\alpha)$ onto the plane $p(\alpha) = 0$:

(a)

(b)

4.4 Derivation of $P_{mp}(\alpha)$ for Bound Systems

In section 5, we will describe a method for deriving an analytical expression for P_{mp} from the Hamiltonian of a system. This method will be applied to some single-term polynomial potentials of the form $V(x) = Kx^s$, ($s \in \mathbb{Z}$). These results are subsequently used in section 6 to examine representative physical systems that are composed of these single-term polynomial potentials:

1. Particle-in-a-Box ($s = 0$)
2. Bouncing Ball ($s = + 1$)
3. Harmonic Oscillator ($s = + 2$)

Description of the particle's motion consists of the following:

1. The equation describing the particle's trajectory.
2. The equation defining the value of P_{mp} along that trajectory.
3. The spectral indices of the constants of motion (e.g., energy, angular momentum, angular momentum spatial orientation, etc.) which satisfy boundary conditions for P_m in phase space.

5 Describing the Mechanics of Systems

Now, we will develop a method for describing the mechanics of systems using the concept of probability density of measurable presence presented above. For simplicity, we develop this method for particles moving:

1. At non-relativistic speeds
2. In a 1-dimensional configuration space, and its corresponding 2- (or 3-, including $\frac{tE}{\hbar}$) dimensional phase space

We often encounter an expression in the analysis that follows, which involves the potential constant K , the mass m of a particle, and \hbar . For notational convenience, we refer to that expression throughout this paper as Ξ , which is defined as follows:

$$\Xi \equiv \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \quad (1)$$

5.1 Application to Systems in One Spatial Dimension

We first apply the model to 1-dimensional systems.

The method developed involves:

1. deriving P_m and P_p from a Hamiltonian with an arbitrary potential.
2. deriving P_m and P_p from Hamiltonians with a single-term polynomial potential.

5.1.1 Deriving P_m and P_p from the Hamiltonian

Expressing the value of P_m along the phase space trajectory of a particle amounts to identifying the set of phase space points on the particle's trajectory and expressing the value of P_m for each of those points. This set of points can be identified using the Hamiltonian that describes the particle's motion.

For simplicity, we will consider here only systems with conservative forces having potentials that depend on position alone and with total energy E being a constant of the motion ($E = T + V$).

We start with the expression for the non-relativistic motion of a particle of mass m in Hamiltonian form:

$$E = \frac{p_x^2}{2m} + V(x)$$

The momentum p_x can be expressed in terms of the position (x) only:

$$p_x(x) = \pm \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))}$$

As $V(x)$ depends only on position, the **probability density of measurability** P_m can be expressed in terms of position alone (as the cosine is an even function, we can use either root of $p_x(x)$):

$$\begin{aligned} P_m &= \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi \cdot x \cdot p_x(x)}{\hbar} - \Phi\right) \\ &= \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi \cdot x \cdot \sqrt{2m(E - V(x))}}{\hbar} - \Phi\right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Taking the particle's **probability density of presence** to be, in general, inversely proportional to the magnitude of the velocity ($\frac{p}{m}$) of the particle, we have for P_p (also in terms of displacement alone):

$$P_p \propto \frac{m}{\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}} \quad (2)$$

We then have the following for the **probability density of measurable presence**:

$$P_{mp} \propto \frac{\cos^2\left(\frac{\pi \cdot x \cdot \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}}{h} - \Phi\right)}{\sqrt{\frac{2}{m}(E-V(x))}} \quad (3)$$

A noteworthy property of this description is that for polynomial potentials, *at the turning point locations* (where $E = V(x)$ and thus the value of P_p itself is undefined), and given the series expansion of the cosine function, we see that the zeros of P_m at those turning points are generally more aggressive than the infinities of P_p at those turning points (in fact, they are always more aggressive than the reciprocal of a polynomial of a *finite* number of terms). This results in finite values ($P_{mp} = 0$) for P_{mp} at those turning points. This coincidence¹⁰ will prove to be convenient in the description of systems.

Interestingly, in this model, the broad behavior of P_{mp} () for bound systems¹¹ arises from both the oscillatory and damping-to-zero-at-turning-points behavior of $\cos^2[x]$ (ultimately due to the phase space scalar field of measurability) combined with the shaping behavior of $\frac{m}{p}$ between turning points. In contrast, in the standard model, the oscillatory behavior arises from a polynomial (e.g., Hermite, Laguerre, etc.), and the damping and shaping behavior arises from the exponential $e^{u(x)}$.

Next, we will examine the behavior of P_m in phase space for a set of single-term polynomial potential functions $V(x)$.

5.1.2 Properties of P_m

In this section, we briefly examine observed properties of P_m in phase space and configuration space.

¹⁰ There may be physical arguments that this is not merely coincidence, but instead is an inevitable restriction on the measurability of an object at rest.

¹¹ i.e., those characterized by oscillatory probability density and damping to zero at the turning points, while being shaped in between turning points by $P_p()$

5.1.2.1 Behavior of P_m in Phase Space

We find it is evident empirically — by inspecting the morphology of graphical plots as the constants of motion are varied — and we can confirm analytically (at least for $s = \pm 1, \pm 2$) that P_m along the phase space trajectory exhibits distinctive “broad” extrema when $\alpha = n\pi \pm \alpha_e$, where α_e is characteristic of the potential and independent of the (values of the) constants of motion. We refer to the extrema at $\alpha = n\pi \pm \alpha_e$ as the **characteristic extrema**. The angle α_e is also independent of the number and positions of additional extrema (both varying with values of the constants of motion), which P_m exhibits. Furthermore, the *value* of P_m itself exhibits extrema (0, 1) at fixed angles $\alpha = n\pi \pm \alpha_e$ for only a spectrum of discrete values of the constants of motion. This fact will be used as a boundary condition in subsequent analysis to determine the spectral indices of the constants of motion of various systems.

We see these observations illustrated in the following figures (in these examples, $s = 2, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{4}, n = 4$), where **plot (a)** shows the extrema of P_m at $\alpha = 0 + \alpha_e, \pi - \alpha_e$ for the spectral index n (blue) and for the spectral index $n + 1$ (orange), while **plot (b)** shows the variation of P_m between its extrema for values between n and $n + 1$ inclusive, e.g., $n, n + 0.1, n + 0.2, \dots, n + 0.8, n + 0.9, n + 1$. **Plot (a)** shows special cases of **plot (b)**:

See appendix C for a graphical illustration of these concepts.

We illustrate the following aspects of the phase space trajectory of a particle that is subject to a potential:

1. phase space trajectory characteristic of the potential (bound and unbound).
2. $P_m(\alpha)$ along the bound portion of the trajectory, showing locations of characteristic extrema.
3. what we will refer to as **space-like** segments of $P_m(\alpha)$, for $\pi - \alpha_e \geq \alpha \geq 0 + \alpha_e$ in phase space.

4. what we will refer to as **momentum-like**¹² segments of $P_m(\alpha)$, for $\pi + \alpha_e \geq \alpha \geq 0 - \alpha_e$ in phase space. These momentum-like segments are interpreted as depicting the "motion" of the particle through phase space while the particle is instantaneously at rest in configuration space (at the turning point).
5. parallel projection of the space-like segment onto configuration space [i.e., the $x(\alpha) - P_m(\alpha)$ plane in phase space].

We will illustrate these aspects below for the potential $V(x) = Kx^2$ in particular (for which $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{4}$, which will be shown later) with $n = 4$, though these aspects are exhibited for all single-term polynomial potentials ($s \neq 0$) and spectral indices.

5.1.2.2 Value of P_m in Regions where $\frac{xp_x}{\hbar}$ is Imaginary

The behavior of $\cos^2(x)$ in regions where $\frac{xp_x}{\hbar}$ is imaginary (i.e., where $2m(E - V(x)) < 0$) and given the identity $\cos(i * u) = \cosh(u)$ where $u \in \Re$ means that P_m is real-valued even when $\frac{xp_x}{\hbar}$ is imaginary, though in such cases its value can be greater than 1. In general, $\cosh(u)$ exhibits non-oscillatory behavior when u is real and oscillatory behavior when u is imaginary, while $\cos(u)$ exhibits the opposite behavior (oscillatory when u is real and non-oscillatory when u is imaginary). Thus, in cases where a particle's trajectory passes through locations in phase space with imaginary values for $\frac{xp_x}{\hbar}$, the value of P_m varies in a non-oscillatory way.

5.1.2.3 Phase Space Trajectory

As the following figure illustrates, the unbound trajectory (repulsive potential) consists of two curves opening to the right and left, while the bound trajectory (attractive potential) consists of a closed curve in the center. The angular location of α_e is indicated by the red dashed lines passing through the origin and crossing through the bound trajectory.

¹² The concept and nature of space-like and momentum-like segments will be clarified and discussed further.

5.1.2.4 $P_m(\alpha)$ Along Bound Phase Space Trajectory, Showing Characteristic Extrema

The characteristic extrema at $\alpha = n\pi \pm \alpha_e$ ($n \in \mathbb{Z}$) delimit space-like and momentum-like segments of $P_m(\alpha)$. The angular location of α_e is indicated by the red dashed lines, which cross through both the bound trajectory at the location of the characteristic extrema.

5.1.2.5 Space-Like Segments of $P_m(\alpha)$

The space-like segments of $P_m(\alpha)$ lie where $0 + \alpha_e \leq \alpha \leq \pi - \alpha_e$ and where $\pi + \alpha_e \leq \alpha \leq 0 - \alpha_e$, while the momentum-like segments lie where $\pi - \alpha_e \leq \alpha \leq \pi + \alpha_e$ and where $0 - \alpha_e \leq \alpha \leq 0 + \alpha_e$. The two space-like segments are shown in the following figure.

5.1.2.6 Projection of Space-Like Segments onto Configuration Space

This depicts the parallel projection of the space-like segment of $P_m(\alpha)$ onto configuration space, giving $P_m(x)$:

We put forth the conjecture that the characteristic extrema of P_m at angle α_e serve the following purposes:

1. To divide the phase space trajectory into segments, which we refer to as space-like and momentum-like. The configuration space representation of P_m will be the parallel projection of the space-like segment of P_m onto the $x - P_m$ plane.
2. To be used as a boundary condition imposed on $P_m(\alpha)$ to determine the discrete spectrum of values of the constants of motion (e.g., energy, angular momentum, etc.) for a bound system. There are other possible reasons for this being a boundary condition¹³.

It should be noted that our conjecture in (1) — that “**The configuration space representation of P_m will be the parallel projection of the space-like segment of P_m onto the $x - P_m$ plane**” — is tentative. It is possible, instead, that the variation of $P_m(\alpha)$ **along the curved, space-like segment of the phase space trajectory** is what should be compared to the probability density distribution of the canonical model in configuration space. However, for some of the polynomial potentials subsequently investigated, the expression for position along the space-like segment of the phase space trajectory, given by:

$$s(\alpha) = \int \sqrt{\left(\frac{dx}{d\alpha}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dp_x}{d\alpha}\right)^2} d\alpha$$

can be difficult to evaluate. Therefore, in this paper, we will initially investigate the parallel projection mentioned in (1).

5.1.3 Deriving P_m for Polynomial Potential of Degree $s \neq 0$

We start by examining the behavior of P_m along the phase space and configuration space trajectories of systems having a single-term polynomial potential function of degree $s \neq 0$:

$$V(x) = Kx^s$$

This will prove to be useful because the representative systems we examine later are composed of these polynomial potentials in one form or another.

For a system with the above polynomial potential and total energy E , we have:

$$E = \frac{p_x^2}{2m} + Kx^s$$

We define the following non-dimensional variables that we can use to express the Hamiltonian in phase space (\mathbb{x}, \mathbb{p}) :

¹³ One possible reason this is a physical boundary condition is that it is the turning point on the bound trajectory and is thus the location where momentum is zero and thus presence cannot be measured — that is, it seems that something can only be measured only if it has non-zero momentum relative to the measurement device. This is a subject proposed for further investigation.

$$\mathbb{x} = \sqrt[s]{x^s \frac{K}{E}} = x \sqrt[s]{\frac{K}{E}}$$

$$\mathbb{p} = \frac{p_x}{\sqrt{2mE}}$$

These allow us to write the Hamiltonian as:

$$\mathbb{p}^2 + \mathbb{x}^s = 1$$

In phase space, we can parametrize (\mathbb{x}, \mathbb{p}) in terms of a central angle α , giving:

$$\mathbb{x} = \cos(\alpha)$$

$$\mathbb{p} = \pm \sqrt{1 - \mathbb{x}^s}$$

$$\mathbb{p} = \pm \sqrt{1 - \cos^s(\alpha)}$$

As the expression under the radical is the square of the momentum, we use its absolute value to ensure a real value for the momentum, giving:

$$\mathbb{p} = \pm \sqrt{|1 - \cos^s(\alpha)|}$$

Equating both expressions respectively for \mathbb{x} and \mathbb{p} , we obtain expressions for x and p_x in terms of α , giving:

$$x(\alpha) = \sqrt[s]{\frac{E}{K}} \cos(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

$$p_x(\alpha) = \sqrt{2mE} |1 - \cos^s(\alpha)|$$

This allows us to write for $\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar}$ in phase space:

$$\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar} = \frac{1}{\hbar} \left(\sqrt[s]{\frac{E}{K}} \cos(\alpha) \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{2mE} |1 - \cos^s(\alpha)| \right)$$

$$= \sqrt[s]{\frac{E}{K}} \sqrt{\frac{2m}{\hbar^2}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{E} |1 - \cos^s(\alpha)| \quad (2)$$

5.1.3.1 Phase Space General Form of P_m

Using the expression obtained in eqn. 5.1.3(2) for $\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar}$, we can write for the phase space form of $P_m(\alpha)$ for single-term polynomials of degree $s \neq 0$:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar} \right]$$

$$= \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt[s]{\frac{E}{K}} \sqrt{\frac{2m}{\hbar^2}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{E} |1 - \cos^s(\alpha)| \right] \quad (1)$$

5.1.3.2 Configuration Space General Form of P_m

Noting the expression for $x(\alpha)$ defined in eqn. 5.1.3(1), we can use $x\sqrt{\frac{K}{E}}$ in place of $\cos(\alpha)$ in the phase space form of P_m obtained in eqn 5.1.3.1(1) to derive the configuration space form of P_m :

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \left(\frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \right) \sqrt{\left| \frac{E}{K} - x^s \right|} \right] \quad (1)$$

We will next derive forms of $P_m(\alpha)$ for specific values of s in phase space in section 5.1.5 and then derive corresponding forms of $P_m(x)$ in configuration space in section 5.1.6.

5.1.3.3 For Specific Values of s

The following sections will derive forms, boundary conditions, spectral indices and expressions for the single-term polynomial potentials with $s = \pm 1, \pm 2$.

5.1.3.3.1 Phase Space Forms of $P_m(\alpha)$

Using the general form for $P_m(\alpha)$ obtained in eqn. 5.1.3.1(1), we now straightforwardly derive the specific forms of $P_m(\alpha)$ for $s = \pm 1, \pm 2$.

For $s = 1$:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mE^3}{\hbar^2 K^2}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{|1 - \cos(\alpha)|} \right]$$

For $s = 2$:

For this case, the expression $[1 - \cos^2(\alpha)]$ is always positive, so we do not need to take the absolute value of the expression under the radical:

$$\begin{aligned} P_m(\alpha) &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mE^2}{\hbar^2 K}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{|1 - \cos^2(\alpha)|} \right] \\ &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mE^2}{\hbar^2 K}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{1 - \cos^2(\alpha)} \right] \\ &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mE^2}{\hbar^2 K}} \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha) \right] \end{aligned}$$

For $s = -1$:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mK^2}{\hbar^2 E}} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{|1 - \sec(\alpha)|} \right]$$

For $s = -2$:

For this case, we will only consider values of α in the first quadrant, where the expression $\sqrt{1 - \sec^2(\alpha)}$, which reduces to $\tan(\alpha)$, is always positive. As a result, we do not need to use the absolute value of the expression under the radical:

$$\begin{aligned} P_m(\alpha) &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{1 - \sec^2(\alpha)} \right] \\ &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{1 - \sec^2(\alpha)} \right] \\ &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \sin(\alpha) \right] \end{aligned}$$

5.1.3.3.2 Applying Boundary Conditions in Phase Space

Treating the extrema of P_m at $\alpha = n\pi \pm \alpha_e$ ($n \in \mathbb{Z}$) as a boundary condition (the boundary nominally being the broad-extrema between the space-like and momentum-like segments of P_m , the physical correlates of which remain to be determined) and then applying this boundary condition to the polynomial-specific forms derived above, we can determine the spectrum of values of the constant(s) of motion that satisfy the boundary conditions for the polynomial-specific forms.

To do so, we solve the following based on the general form of $\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar}$ obtained in eqn. (9) for constants of the motion (E , or K , as we will see for $s = -2$, where E is eliminated from the equation) in terms of the spectral index q (where $q \in \mathbb{Z}$), as well as K , m , \hbar :

$$\pi \sqrt{\frac{E}{K}} \sqrt{\frac{2m}{\hbar^2}} \cos(\alpha_e) \sqrt{E |1 - \cos^s(\alpha_e)|} = q \frac{\pi}{2}$$

For $s = 1$:

With $\alpha_e = \arccos\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)$, we obtain the spectrum of values satisfying the boundary condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi \sqrt{\frac{2mE^3}{\hbar^2 K^2}} \cos\left[\arccos\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)\right] \sqrt{|1 - \cos\left[\arccos\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)\right]|} &= q \frac{\pi}{2} \\ E_q &= \left[\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \right)^2 \frac{\hbar^2 K^2}{2m} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \end{aligned}$$

For $s = 2$:

With $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{4}$, we obtain the spectrum of values satisfying the boundary condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi \sqrt{\frac{2mE^2}{\hbar^2 K}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) &= q \frac{\pi}{2} \\ E_q &= q \hbar \sqrt{\frac{K}{2m}} \end{aligned}$$

For $s = -1$:

With $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{3}$, we obtain the spectrum of values satisfying the boundary condition:

$$\pi \sqrt{\frac{2mK^2}{\hbar^2 E}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right) \sqrt{\left|1 - \sec\left(\frac{\pi}{3}\right)\right|} = q \frac{\pi}{2}$$

$$E_q = \frac{2mK^2}{\hbar^2 q^2}$$

For $s = -2$:

With $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{2}$, we obtain the spectrum of values satisfying the boundary condition:

$$\pi \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = q \frac{\pi}{2}$$

$$K_q = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \cdot \left(\frac{q}{2}\right)^2$$

There are two interesting things to note for the case where $s = -2$.

1. Only the potential constant K is constrained by the boundary condition, whereas the energy E is not. We will see that, as this potential appears in the Hamiltonian for the central potential, this amounts to the spectral indexing of angular momentum (where $K = \frac{L^2}{2m}$, with the potential containing the term $\frac{L^2}{2mr^2}$).
2. There is no space-like segment along $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space. There is only a momentum-like segment. Perhaps this can be interpreted as there being — with strictly angular motion — no spatial motion along the radius.

5.1.3.3.3 Phase Space Expressions for $P_m(\alpha)$

Applying the spectral index boundary condition results of 5.1.3.3.2 to the specific forms of $P_m(\alpha)$ for $s = \pm 1, \pm 2$ obtained in 5.1.3.3.1, we derive the specific expressions of $P_m(\alpha)$ for $s = \pm 1, \pm 2$.

For $s = 1$:

Substituting the value for E_q for $s = 1$ back into the specific form for $P_m(\alpha)_{s=1}$, we obtain:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \pi \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{|1 - \cos(\alpha)|} \right]$$

For $s = 2$:

Substituting the value for E_q for $s = 2$ back into the specific form for $P_m(\alpha)_{s=2}$, we obtain:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 [q \pi \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha)]$$

For $s = -1$:

Substituting the value for E_q for $s = -1$ back into the specific form for $P_m(\alpha)_{s=-1}$, we obtain:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 [q \pi \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{|1 - \sec(\alpha)|}]$$

For $s = -2$:

Substituting the value for K_q for $s = -2$ back into the specific form for $P_m(\alpha)_{s=-2}$, we obtain:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2\left[\frac{q}{2}\pi \sin(\alpha)\right]$$

5.1.3.3.3.1 Phase Space Expressions for Space-Like Segments of $s(\alpha)$

Now, we evaluate the indefinite integral yielding the phase space trajectory parametric curve.

We start by recalling that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{X} &= x\sqrt{\frac{K}{E}} \\ \mathbb{P} &= \frac{p_x}{\sqrt{2mE}} \\ \mathbb{X}(\alpha) &= \cos(\alpha) \\ \mathbb{P}_x(\alpha) &= \pm \sqrt{1 - \cos^s(\alpha)} \end{aligned}$$

With the equation for the phase space trajectory curve being the indefinite integral:

$$s(\alpha) = \int \sqrt{\left(\frac{d\mathbb{X}(\alpha)}{d\alpha}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{d\mathbb{P}_x(\alpha)}{d\alpha}\right)^2} d\alpha$$

and considering that:

$$\frac{d\mathbb{X}(\alpha)}{d\alpha} = -\sin(\alpha)$$

we obtain:

$$s(\alpha) = \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{d}{d\alpha}\left(\sqrt{|1 - \cos^s(\alpha)|}\right)\right)^2} d\alpha$$

For specific values of $s \neq 0$, we obtain the following.

For $s = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{d}{d\alpha}\left(\sqrt{|1 - \cos(\alpha)|}\right)\right)^2} d\alpha \\ &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \frac{\sin^2(\alpha)}{4(1-\cos(\alpha))}} d\alpha \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{4\cos(\alpha)-5} \cdot \sqrt{\cos(\alpha)-2\cos(2\alpha)+3} \cdot \sec\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{2} \cdot \sinh^{-1}\left(2\sqrt{2} \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)\right) + 4\sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)\sqrt{5-4\cos(\alpha)}\right)}{8\sqrt{-(5-4\cos(\alpha))^2}} + c \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{For } s(\alpha) = \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \frac{\sin^2(\alpha)}{4(1-\cos(\alpha))} + 1} d\alpha$$

=

For $s = 2$:

$$\begin{aligned} s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{d}{d\alpha} \left(\sqrt{|1 - \cos^2(\alpha)|} \right) \right)^2} d\alpha \\ &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \cos^2(\alpha)} d\alpha \\ &= \alpha + c \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \cos^2(\alpha) + 1} d\alpha \\ &= \sqrt{2}\alpha + c \end{aligned}$$

For $s = -1$:

$$\begin{aligned} s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{d}{d\alpha} \left(\sqrt{|1 - \sec(\alpha)|} \right) \right)^2} d\alpha \\ &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{\tan(\alpha) \cdot \sec(\alpha) \cdot (\sec(\alpha) - 1)}{2|1 - \sec(\alpha)|^{3/2}} \right)^2} d\alpha \\ &=? + c \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{\tan(\alpha) \cdot \sec(\alpha) \cdot (\sec(\alpha) - 1)}{2|1 - \sec(\alpha)|^{3/2}} \right)^2 + 1} d\alpha \\ &=? + c \end{aligned}$$

For $s = -2$:

$$\begin{aligned} s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{d}{d\alpha} \left(\sqrt{|1 - \sec^2(\alpha)|} \right) \right)^2} d\alpha \\ &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{\tan^3(\alpha) \cdot \sec^2(\alpha)}{|\tan(\alpha)|^3} \right)^2} d\alpha \\ &=? + c \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{For } s(\alpha) &= \int \sqrt{\sin^2(\alpha) + \left(\frac{\tan^3(\alpha) \cdot \sec^2(\alpha)}{|\tan(\alpha)|^3} \right)^2 + 1} d\alpha \\ &=? + c \end{aligned}$$

5.1.3.3.4 Turning Points

Turning points in configuration space are obtained by parallel projection of the points on $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space that are at the locations of characteristic extrema ($\alpha = 0 + \alpha_e$ and $\alpha = \pi - \alpha_e$). The turning point values $x = \pm x_0$ are obtained from the expression for $x(\alpha)$ above:

$$x(\alpha) = \sqrt{\frac{E}{K}} \cos(\alpha)$$

yielding:

$$\begin{aligned} +x_0 &= x(0 + \alpha_e) = \sqrt{\frac{E}{K}} \cos(0 + \alpha_e) \\ -x_0 &= x(\pi - \alpha_e) = \sqrt{\frac{E}{K}} \cos(\pi - \alpha_e) \end{aligned}$$

For specific values of $s \neq 0$, we obtain the following.

For $s = 1$, $\alpha_e = \arccos\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)$:

$$x_0 = \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{E}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \left(+\frac{2}{3}\right)$$

For $s = 2$, $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{4}$:

$$x_0 = \sqrt{\frac{q}{E}} \cdot \left(+\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}\right)$$

For $s = -1$, $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{3}$:

$$x_0 = \left(\frac{q}{E}\right)^2 \cdot \left(+\frac{1}{2}\right)$$

For $s = -2$, $\alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{2}$:

$$x_0 = \sqrt{\frac{Kq}{E}} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{\hbar q}{2\sqrt{2m}} \cdot \frac{1}{E}\right) \cdot (0) = 0$$

5.1.3.3.5 Configuration Space Expressions for $P_m(x)$

Using the form of $P_m(x)$ obtained above:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \left(\frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \right) \sqrt{\left| \frac{E}{K} - x^s \right|} \right]$$

We derive $P_m(x)$ for specific values of s by:

For $s = 1$:

Substituting the value for E_q (obtained above for $s = 1$ by imposing the boundary condition in phase space) into the form for $P_m(x)$ and restricting the domain to lie between the turning point and the origin, we obtain (introducing in appendix B a notational convention for the domain of evaluation of an expression):

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_m(x) &= \cos^2 \left[\pi x \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \sqrt{\left| \frac{1}{K} \left[\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \right)^2 \frac{\hbar^2 K^2}{2m} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} - x \right|} \right]_{0}^{\left(\frac{E_q}{K} \right) \cdot \cos \left(0 + \arccos \left(\frac{2}{3} \right) \right)} \\
 &= \cos^2 \left[\pi x \Xi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - x \right|} \right]_{0}^{\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \left(+ \frac{2}{3} \right)}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $s = 2$:

Substituting the value for E_q (obtained above for $s = 2$ by imposing the boundary condition in phase space) into the form for $P_m(x)$ and recalling the reasoning in the derivation of the phase space form of P_m for $s = 2$ for not taking the absolute value of the expression under the radical, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_m(x) &= \cos^2 \left[\pi x \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \sqrt{\frac{1}{K} q \hbar \sqrt{\frac{K}{2m}} - x^2} \right]_{\sqrt{\frac{E_q}{K}} \cdot \cos \left(\pi - \frac{\pi}{4} \right)}^{\sqrt{\frac{E_q}{K}} \cdot \cos \left(0 + \frac{\pi}{4} \right)} \\
 &= \cos^2 \left[\pi x \Xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2} \right]_{\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi}} \cdot \left(-\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right)}^{\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi}} \cdot \left(+\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right)}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $s = -1$:

Substituting the value for E_q (obtained above for $s = -1$ by imposing the boundary condition in phase space) into the form for $P_m(x)$ and restricting the domain to lie between the turning point and the origin, we obtain:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \frac{\sqrt{2mK}}{\hbar} \sqrt{\left| \frac{1}{K} \frac{2mK^2}{\hbar^2 q^2} - \frac{1}{x} \right|} \right]_{0}^{\frac{K}{E_q} \cdot \cos \left(0 + \frac{\pi}{3} \right)}$$

$$= \cos^2 \left[\pi x \mathbb{E} \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\mathbb{E}}{q} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{x} \right|} \right]_{0}^{\left(\frac{q}{\mathbb{E}} \right)^2 \cdot \left(+\frac{1}{2} \right)}$$

For $s = -2$:

There is no space-like segment of $P_m(\alpha)$ to parallel-project onto configuration space for this polynomial potential, though there is a momentum-like segment. We can parallel-project the momentum-like segment of $P_m(\alpha)$ either onto:

1. Configuration space, giving:

2. Momentum space, giving:

Substituting the value for K (obtained above for $s = -2$ by imposing boundary conditions in phase space) into the form for $P_m(x)$, we obtain:

$$K_q = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \cdot \left(\frac{q}{2} \right)^2$$

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \left(\frac{q}{2} \right) \sqrt{\left| E - \frac{8m}{\hbar^2 q^2} - \frac{1}{x^2} \right|} \right]$$

Defining $Q = \frac{q}{2}$, we have:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x Q \sqrt{\left| E \cdot \left(\frac{\sqrt{2m}}{Q\hbar} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{x^2} \right|} \right]$$

$$= \cos^2 \left[\pi x \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar} \right)^2 - \frac{Q^2}{x^2} \right|} \right]$$

By reversing the roles of E and K in the definition of Ξ , we define $\xi \equiv \frac{\sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar}$, giving:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \sqrt{\left| \xi^2 - \frac{Q^2}{x^2} \right|} \right]$$

5.1.3.3.6 Plots of P_m in Phase Space and Configuration Space

The following plots of P_m for select polynomial potentials illustrate the behaviors of P_m described above in both phase space and configuration space.

For the following plots of P_m :

1. For 2D plots, the vertical axis is momentum p_x , and the horizontal axis is spatial displacement x , while, additionally, for 3D plots, the z axis is P_m .
2. **Plot (a)** depicts the phase space trajectory in the $x - p_x$ plane, with the inner closed shape corresponding to an attractive potential and the outer open shapes corresponding to a repulsive potential. The characteristic angle α_e is indicated by the diagonal lines.
3. **Plot (b)** depicts the phase space trajectory through the scalar field, illustrating why the value of P_m varies as it does along the trajectory shown in plot (c). For each plot, the scalar field is expressed in terms of the “natural” spectral index q of the system:

$$P_m = \cos^2 \left[\left(\pi \cdot q \cdot x \cdot p_x \right) - \Phi_q \right]$$

4. **Plot (c)** depicts P_m ($0 \leq P_m \leq 1$) along the phase space trajectory for the attractive potential, while $n\pi \pm \alpha_e$ is indicated by diagonal lines.
5. **Plot (d)** depicts the parallel projection of (c) onto the $x - P_m$ plane (in configuration space).
6. **Plot (e)** depicts the space-like segment of P_m along the phase space trajectory (delimited from the momentum-like segments by the extremum value of P_m at $n\pi \pm \alpha_e$), while $n\pi \pm \alpha_e$ is indicated by diagonal lines.
7. **Plot (f)** depicts the parallel projection of (e) – between $\pi - \alpha_e$ and $0 + \alpha_e$ – onto the $x - P_m$ plane (in configuration space).

For $s = 0$, $n = 5$, $L = 3$, $\alpha_e = \arccos \left(\frac{2n}{L^2} \right)$:

For $s = 1, n = 5, \alpha_e = \arccos\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)$:

For $s = 2, n = 5, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{4}$:

For $s = -1, n = 5, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{3}$:

For $s = -2, n = 5, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{2}$:

5.1.3.3.7 Interpreting the Value of $P_m(\alpha)$ along a Particle Phase Space Trajectory

The probability density of measurability P_m at a given position/momentum location in phase space indicates the probability density of being able to measure a particle at that phase space location, varying between 0 and 1. As this probability density is given by a periodic function (cosine), for at least a certain set of phase space trajectories, it will vary cyclically along those trajectories (and, in general, though perhaps not always, along the particle's corresponding configuration space trajectories, which derive from -- are parallel projections of -- the phase space trajectories).

We assume that every given form of potential energy in a bound system has a classical spatial probability density distribution that indicates the probability density of the particle being present at a location on its configuration space trajectory. It is the parallel projection of the probability density of measurable presence along a particle's phase space trajectory onto the phase space plane $p_x = p_0$ that portrays the probability density of measurable presence for the particle at a location in configuration space.

The values of P_m near the turning points of oscillatory motion empirically exhibit a "well" of low (depending on Φ) probability density of measurability (~ 0), with $P_m = 0$ occurring at the turning points.

5.1.3.3.8 Configuration Space Expressions for P_p

Using the expression for p_x (obtained in deriving the expression for P_m in configuration space):

$$p_x = \Xi \sqrt{\left| \frac{E}{K} - x^s \right|}$$

we readily obtain an expression for P_p in configuration space:

$$P_p(x) \propto \frac{1}{v} = \frac{m}{p_x} = \frac{m}{\Xi \sqrt{\left| \frac{E}{K} - x^s \right|}}$$

Using the results for p_x obtained for specific polynomials, we derive corresponding expressions for $P_p(x)_s$:

For $s = 1$:

Substituting the value for E_q (obtained above for $s = 1$ by imposing the boundary condition in phase space) into the expression for $P_m(x)$ above, we obtain:

$$P_p(x) = \left[\frac{m}{\Xi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - x \right|}} \right]_{\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \left(+\frac{2}{3} \right)}^0$$

For $s = 2$:

Substituting the value for E_q (obtained above for $s = 2$ by imposing the boundary condition in phase space) into the expression for $P_m(x)$ above (with $s = 2$), we obtain:

$$P_p(x) = \left[\frac{m}{\Xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2}} \right]_{\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi}} \cdot \left(+\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right)}^{\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi}} \cdot \left(-\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right)}$$

For $s = -1$:

Substituting the value for E_q (obtained above for $s = -1$ by imposing the boundary condition in phase space) into the expression for $P_m(x)$ above, we obtain:

$$P_p(x) = \left[\frac{m}{\Xi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\Xi}{q} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{x} \right|}} \right]_{\left(\frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^2 \cdot \left(+\frac{1}{2} \right)}^0$$

For $s = -2$:

With $\sqrt{Q} = \frac{q}{2}$:

$$P_p(x) = \left[\frac{m}{\sqrt{Q} \sqrt{\left| \frac{\left(\frac{\sqrt{2m}}{h} \right)^2}{Q} - \frac{1}{x^2} \right|}} \right]_{\left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{E_q}} \right) \cdot \cos\left(0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \right)}^{\left(\sqrt{\frac{K}{E_q}} \right) \cdot \cos\left(\pi - \frac{\pi}{2} \right)}$$

5.1.3.3.9 Plots of P_p and P_{mp} in Configuration Space

The following plots of P_p and P_{mp} for select polynomial potentials illustrate the behaviors of P_p described above and the behavior of P_m and P_p combined as P_{mp} in configuration space.

For the following plots of P_p and P_{mp} :

1. The vertical axis is the probability density $P_p(x)$ and $P_{mp}(x)$, and the horizontal axis is the spatial displacement x .
2. **(a)** Depicts the probability density $P_m(x)$ along the configuration space displacement x . This is **(e)** in the previous section.
3. **(b)** depicts both $P_p(x)$ and $P_{mp}(x)$ along the configuration space displacement x
4. **(c)** depicts $P_{mp}(x)$ along the configuration space displacement x

For $s = 1$:

(a)

(b)

(c)

For $s = 2$:

(a)

(b)

(c)

For $s = -1$:

(a)

(b)

(c)

For $s = -2$:

(a)

(b)

(c)

5.1.4 Deriving P_m for Polynomial Potential of Degree $s = 0$

Starting with the potential:

$$V(x) = Kx^0 = K$$

We have the Hamiltonian:

$$E = \frac{p_x^2}{2m} + K$$

The momentum of this system is a constant value:

$$p_x = \pm \sqrt{2m(E - K)}$$

Following the method used to derive P_m for polynomial potentials of degree $s \neq 0$, we define the following non-dimensional variables in phase space, with the displacement scaled by an arbitrary length L (as there is no natural scale arising from a turning point):

$$\mathbb{x} = \frac{x}{L}$$

$$\mathbb{p}_x = \frac{p_x}{\sqrt{2m(E-K)}}$$

In terms of these, the Hamiltonian takes the form:

$$\mathbb{p}_x^2 = 1$$

In phase space, we can parametrize \mathbb{x} in terms of a central angle α , while \mathbb{p}_x is a constant:

$$\mathbb{x} = \cos(\alpha)$$

$$\mathbb{p}_x = \pm 1$$

Equating both expressions, respectively, for \mathbb{x} and \mathbb{p} , we obtain expressions for x and p_x in terms of α , giving:

$$x(\alpha) = L \cos(\alpha)$$

$$p_x(\alpha) = \pm \sqrt{2m(E - K)}$$

We can now evaluate $P_m(\alpha)$, as we write:

$$\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar} = \frac{(L \cdot \cos(\alpha)) \cdot (\pm \sqrt{2m(E-K)})}{\hbar}$$

5.1.4.1 Phase Space Form of P_m

Using the expression obtained above for $\frac{x(\alpha) \cdot p_x(\alpha)}{\hbar}$, we can write for the phase space form of $P_m(\alpha)$:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\pi L \frac{\sqrt{2m(E-K)}}{\hbar} \cos(\alpha) - \Phi \right]$$

5.1.4.2 Configuration Space Form of P_m

Noting the expression for $x(\alpha)$ defined in 5.1.4, we can use $\frac{x(\alpha)}{L}$ in place of $\cos(\alpha)$ in the phase space form of P_m obtained in 5.1.4.1 to derive the configuration space form of P_m :

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{\pi \cdot x \cdot \sqrt{2m(E-K)}}{\hbar} - \Phi \right]$$

5.1.4.3 Applying Boundary Conditions in Phase Space

If we impose a boundary condition of continuity at the points $x(\alpha) = \pm L$ (and thus $\cos(\alpha) = \pm 1$):

$$\pi L \frac{\sqrt{2m(E-K)}}{\hbar} \cos(\alpha) - \Phi = q \frac{\pi}{2}$$

We obtain for the energy E :

$$E_q = \frac{\hbar^2 q^2}{2mL^2} + K$$

5.1.4.4 Phase Space Expression for P_m

Substituting this result for the energy E_q back into the form of $P_m(\alpha)$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P_m(\alpha) &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \cdot \sqrt{q^2 + \Xi^2 L^2} \cdot \cos(\alpha) - \Phi \right] \\ &= \cos^2 \left[\pi \cdot L \cos(\alpha) \cdot \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{L^2} + \Xi^2} - \Phi \right] \end{aligned}$$

Note that for the case where $K = 0$ (thus $\Xi = 0$), this reduces to:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 [\pi \cdot q \cdot \cos(\alpha) - \Phi]$$

5.1.4.5 Configuration Space Expression for P_m

Using the phase space expression for $P_m(\alpha)$ and expressing $\cos(\alpha)$ in terms of x :

$$\cos(\alpha) = \frac{x(\alpha)}{L}$$

We then obtain the configuration space expression for $P_m(x)$:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{L^2} + \Xi^2} - \Phi \right]$$

Note that for the case where $K = 0$ (thus $\Xi = 0$), this reduces to:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{\pi \cdot q \cdot x}{L} - \Phi \right]$$

5.2 Probability Density Node Deviations from Canonical Model

It is consistently the case that nodes in the probability density distribution for this model do not strictly align with those in the canonical model (except for Particle-In-A-Box, where the potential is $V = 0$), no matter the choice of scaling for the displacement. It is possible (as will be seen for systems examined in sections 6.2.3.2 and 6.3.3.2) to choose a scaling factor that derives from a relationship between outer nodes of this model and corresponding outer nodes of the respective canonical models, which aligns the probability density distributions of this model very closely to those of the canonical model. But of course this requires knowledge of the canonical model (though perhaps those outer nodes could be determined empirically) to which we are here presenting an alternative, and so is inferior to deriving a similarly efficacious (or better) scaling factor from the physics of the systems themselves.

6 Application to Representative Systems

We will now apply the model for describing motion to several representative systems, many of which correspond directly to the general polynomial potentials examined earlier.

6.1 Particle In a Box (PIB): $V(x) = 0$

For brevity, we will hereafter refer to the particle-in-a-box system as PIB.

The PIB system is the special case of a system with a constant potential ($s = 0$), where $K = 0$.

6.1.1 Energy

Using the results of section 5.1.4.3, with $K = 0$, we have the following for the energy:

$$E_q = \frac{\hbar^2 q^2}{2mL^2}$$

6.1.2 P_m in Phase Space

For $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space, we have:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \cdot q \cdot \cos(\alpha) - \Phi_q \right]_0^\pi$$

Following is a plot of the phase space trajectory, and of $P_m(\alpha)$ along that trajectory, for the PIB system (for the plot, $n = 5$, $L = 3$):

6.1.3 P_m , P_p and P_{mp} in Configuration Space

For $P_m(x)$ in configuration space, we have:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2\left[\frac{q\pi x}{L} - \Phi_q\right]$$

The PIB system describes the motion of a particle confined to a well bounded by an infinite potential in the region $x \leq 0$, $x \geq L$, while inside this well the potential is zero. The PIB boundary condition is $P_m = 0$ at $x = 0, L$, which is satisfied when $\Phi = \frac{\pi}{2}$, giving:

$$P_m(x) = \sin^2\left[\frac{q\pi x}{L}\right]_0^L$$

Normalization of P_m gives:

$$\int_0^{+L} \sin^2\left[\frac{q\pi x}{L}\right] dx = \frac{L}{2}$$

and thus the normalization constant $A = \frac{2}{L}$, giving:

$$P_m(x) = \frac{2}{L} \sin^2\left[\frac{q\pi x}{L}\right]_0^L$$

The configuration space plot of $P_m(x)$ along the trajectory is:

Because the particle's momentum is constant, its probability of presence along the configuration space trajectory is unity ($P_p = 1$), giving a probability density of measurable presence:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{mp}(x) &= P_m(x) \cdot 1 \\ &= \frac{2}{L} \sin^2 \left[\frac{q\pi x}{L} \right] \end{aligned}$$

6.1.4 Correspondence to Canonical Quantum Solution

Note that this model yields an expression for the probability density distribution that is identical to the expression for $|\phi_n|^2$ in canonical quantum mechanics:

$$|\phi_n|^2 = \frac{2}{L} \sin^2 \left(\frac{n\pi x}{L} \right)$$

6.2 Bouncing Ball: $V(x) = mgx$

The Hamiltonian of the bouncing ball system:

$$E = \frac{p_x^2}{2m} + mgx$$

is equivalent to the single-term polynomial potential for $s = 1$, thus we use the results from section 5.1.3.3 to describe the bouncing ball system. The constant K of the polynomial potential is mg in this system:

$$K = mg$$

6.2.1 Energy

Starting with the energy of the $s = 1$ system obtained in 5.1.3.3.2:

$$E_q = \left[\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \right)^2 \frac{\hbar^2 K^2}{2m} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

We thus obtain for the energy:

$$E_q = \left[\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \right)^2 \frac{\hbar^2 g^2 m}{2} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

If we define:

$$Q = \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

Then, the energy can be expressed as:

$$E_q = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\hbar^2 m g^2}{2}} \cdot Q$$

6.2.2 P_m in Phase Space

For $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space, we have:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 \left[\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \pi \cos(\alpha) \sqrt{|1 - \cos(\alpha)|} \right]_0^\pi$$

The following is a plot of the phase space trajectory and of $P_m(\alpha)$ along that trajectory for the bouncing ball system (for the following illustrations, $n = 5$). Plot (a) depicts the full phase space trajectory, while plot (b) depicts only the space-like segments.

6.2.3 P_m , P_p and P_{mp} in Configuration Space

In configuration space, we have for the turning points $\pm x_0$:

$$x_0 = \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \left(+ \frac{2}{3} \right)$$

The bouncing ball system describes the motion of a particle bouncing (perfectly elastically) on a rigid floor in a uniform gravitational field. The floor is at the origin of the coordinate system, so x varies from 0 to the turning point, giving $P_m(x)$ as:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \Xi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - x \right|} \right]_0^{+x_0}$$

We then define the scaled displacement as follows:

$$\xi = z \cdot \sigma$$

Using this, we obtain an expression for $P_m(\xi)$ having the same scale as the canonical model:

$$P_m(\xi) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \xi \Xi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}q}{4\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - \xi \right|} \right] \Bigg|_{0}^{+\frac{1}{\sigma} \cdot \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}q}{4\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} = +Z_q}$$

the turning points of which are, by design, identical to those of the canonical solution (with suitable choice of units for Ξ):

$$\xi_0^n \approx \pm Z_q$$

Using the same form as above for $P_{mp}(x)$ but replacing x with the scaled displacement ξ , we have:

$$P_m(\xi) = \frac{\cos^2 \left[\pi \xi \Xi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}q}{4\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - \xi \right|} \right]}{\pi \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}q}{4\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - \xi \right|}} \Bigg|_{0}^{+\frac{1}{\sigma} \cdot \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}q}{4\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} = +Z_q}$$

With this, we produce the following plot showing this model (red) and the classical probability density distribution (green), along with the canonical model (blue) – in this example, $n = 20$:

6.2.3.2 Scaled to Canonical Model Outer Minimum

We can further expand or shrink $P_{mp}(\xi)$ by an additional, mathematically arbitrary scaling factor f_σ , which we choose based on the relationship between the outer minimum of $P_{mp}(\xi)$ (the minima of $P_{mp}(\xi)$ can be determined analytically) and the outer minimum of the canonical model (the outer zero of the Airy function). Choosing the minimum r_{pc} nearest the turning point for the canonical solution (obtained analytically or numerically) and the corresponding minimum r_{pt} (i.e., nearest the turning point for $P_{mp}(\xi)$), we define:

$$r_{pt\sigma} = r_{pt} \cdot \sigma$$

which we use to define f_σ as the following ratio of these two corresponding minima:

$$f_\sigma = \frac{r_{pt\sigma}}{r_{pc}}$$

We then incorporate this factor into the definition of ξ , which yields a probability density distribution that scales to the outer node of the canonical model:

$$\xi = x \cdot \sigma \cdot f_\sigma$$

The result, depicted graphically, is:

6.2.4 Correspondence to Canonical Quantum Solution

Consider the canonical quantum solution, in which

$$l = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^2g}}$$

$$E_n = mgl \cdot z_n$$

giving for the energy

$$E_n = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\hbar^2 mg^2}{2}} \cdot z_n$$

$$z_n \approx \left[\frac{3\pi}{2} \left(n - \frac{1}{4} \right) \right]^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

In contrast, this model yields for the energy:

$$E_q = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\hbar^2 mg^2}{2}} \cdot Q_q$$

$$Q_q = \left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} q \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

We see that this differs from the canonical solution by the factor $\left(\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right)$ and the offset $\left(\frac{1}{4} \right)$ of the energy spectral index.

6.2.5 Mathematical Similarity to Canonical Quantum Solution

There is a degree of mathematical similarity between the analytical description of the system in this model and in the canonical model.

The series expansion of this description is of the order:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos^2 \left[\pi z \Xi \sqrt{\left(\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{q}{\Xi} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} - |z|} \right] &\simeq \cos^2 \left(\sqrt{z^3} \right) \\ \cos^2 \left(\sqrt{z^3} \right) &= 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \cdot \frac{(z^3)^k \cdot 2^{(-1+2k)}}{(2k)!} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-z^3)^k \cdot 2^{(-1+2k)}}{(2k)!} \end{aligned}$$

The series expansion of the canonical description is of the order:

$$Ai(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z^3)^k \cdot 3^{-\left(\frac{2}{3}+2k\right)}}{k!} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)\left(\frac{2}{3}\right)_k} - \frac{\sqrt[3]{3} \cdot z}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{3}\right)\left(\frac{4}{3}\right)_k} \right)$$

6.3 Harmonic Oscillator: $V(x) = \frac{Kx^2}{2}$

Previous results for the polynomial potential where $s = 2$ apply directly to the harmonic oscillator.

6.3.1 Energy

Employing the following definitions typically used in treatments of the Harmonic Oscillator:

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \frac{\mathcal{K}}{2} \\ \omega_0 &= \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{K}}{m}} \end{aligned}$$

and using the energy obtained in 5.1.3.3.2 for the polynomial potential where $s = 2$:

$$E_q = q\hbar \sqrt{\frac{K}{2m}}$$

while also noting that the spectral index for the harmonic oscillator is typically zero-based (whereas in this model, it is one-based), and thus defining:

$$q = 2n + 1$$

we obtain an expression for the energy of the system:

$$E_q = \hbar \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{K}}{4m}} \cdot (2n + 1)$$

$$= \hbar \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{K}}{m}} \cdot \frac{1}{2}(2n + 1)$$

In terms of the index n , the energy is expressed as:

$$E_n = \hbar \omega_0 \cdot \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

6.3.2 P_m in Phase Space

For $P_m(\alpha)$ in phase space, we have:

$$P_m(\alpha) = \cos^2 [q\pi \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha)]$$

The following is a plot of the phase space trajectory, the value of $P_m(\alpha)$ along that trajectory, and the parallel projection of the space-like segments of $P_m(\alpha)$ onto the plane $p = 0$ for the harmonic oscillator (in the following illustration, $n = 5$):

6.3.3 P_m , P_p and P_{mp} in Configuration Space

In configuration space, we have for the turning points $\pm x_0$:

$$x_0 = \sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi}} \cdot \left(+ \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

The harmonic oscillator has a mass moving between the turning points, with $P_m(x)$ being:

$$P_m(x) = \cos^2 \left[\pi x \Xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2} \right]_{-x_0}^{+x_0}$$

The configuration space plot of $P_m(x)$ along the displacement x shows the probability density of measurability description of this movement (in this example, $n = 5$):

Next, we have for $P_p(x)$:

$$P_p(x) = \frac{1}{\pi\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2}}$$

and for $P_{mp}(x)$, with normalization constant A_{mp} :

$$A_{mp} = \left(\int_{-x_0}^{+x_0} \frac{\cos^2\left[\pi x \Xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2}\right]}{\pi\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2}} \right)^{-1}$$

we thus obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{mp}(x) &= A_{mp} \cdot P_m(x) \cdot P_p(x) \\ &= A_{mp} \cdot \frac{\cos^2\left[\pi x \Xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2}\right]}{\pi\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi} - x^2}} \end{aligned}$$

6.3.3.1 Displacement Scaled to Indexing of Canonical Model

We can readily adapt the result obtained above to typical treatments of the Harmonic Oscillator by defining a dimensionless scaled displacement ξ , yielding a description having the same scale as the canonical model (i.e., having turning points at $\pm \xi_0^n = \pm \sqrt{2n + 1}$).

The turning point in this model is:

$$x_0^q = \sqrt{\frac{q}{2\Xi}}$$

Using the turning point in the canonical model, we obtain the scaling factor σ :

$$x_0^q = \xi_0^n \cdot \sigma$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{q}{2\xi} \cdot \frac{1}{(2n+1)}}$$

We then define the scaled displacement as follows:

$$\xi = x \cdot \sigma$$

Separately, while the spectral index in the canonical model is zero based, in this model it is 1 based, which difference we reconcile by defining:

$$q = n + 1$$

Using this definition for ξ , we obtain an expression for $P_m(\xi)$ having the same scale as the canonical model:

$$P_m(\xi) = \cos^2 \left[\pi \xi \xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\xi} - \xi^2} \right]_{\left(\sqrt{\frac{q}{2\xi} \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma}} \right) = +\sqrt{2n+1}}^{\left(\sqrt{\frac{q}{2\xi} \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma}} \right) = -\sqrt{2n+1}}$$

The turning points of which are, by design, identical to those of the canonical solution (with suitable choice of units for ξ):

$$\xi_0^n = \pm \sqrt{2n + 1}$$

Using the same form as above for $P_{mp}(x)$ – but replacing x with the scaled displacement ξ :

$$P_{mp}(\xi) = \left[\frac{\cos^2 \left[\pi \xi \xi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\xi} - \xi^2} \right]}{\pi \sqrt{\frac{q}{\xi} - \xi^2}} \right]_{\left(\sqrt{\frac{q}{2\xi} \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma}} \right) = +\sqrt{2n+1}}^{\left(\sqrt{\frac{q}{2\xi} \cdot \frac{1}{\sigma}} \right) = -\sqrt{2n+1}}$$

we produce the following plots: this model (red); the classical probability density distribution (green); and the canonical model (blue). The non-dimensional turning points $\xi_0^n = \sqrt{2n + 1}$ are indicated by the vertical black dashed lines. Some gaps or irregularities in the plots are graphing artifacts and do not represent actual values from the models.

n=3

n=6

n=9

n=14

n=39

n=64

n=128

n=256

n=360

Beyond the broad similarity between the results of the PKM model and CQM, there are some noteworthy differences between the probability density distributions of the two models:

- 1) In this model, the probability density of measurable presence at the classical turning point is uniformly zero, whereas the probability density in the canonical model at the classical turning points is never zero (though increasingly close to zero for higher spectral indices).
- 2) The heights of the probability peaks nearest the turning points are greater in the canonical model than in this model. This is due, at least in part, to the turning points

always being at the outer edge of the two outermost peaks in this model. However, as the spectral index increases, the outermost peaks in this model approach the classical turning point.

6.3.3.2 Scaled to Canonical Model Outer Minimum

We can further expand or shrink $P_{mp}(\xi)$ by an additional, mathematically arbitrary scaling factor f_σ , which we choose based on the relationship between the outer minimum of $P_{mp}(\xi)$ (the minima of $P_{mp}(\xi)$ can be determined analytically) and the outer minimum of the canonical model (the outer zero of the Hermite polynomial). Choosing the minimum r_{pt} nearest the turning point for the canonical solution (obtained analytically or numerically) and the corresponding minimum $r_{pt\sigma}$ (i.e., nearest the turning point for $P_{mp}(\xi)$), we define:

$$r_{pt\sigma} = r_{pt} \cdot \sigma$$

which we use to define f_σ as the following ratio of these two corresponding minima:

$$f_\sigma = \frac{r_{pt\sigma}}{r_{pt}}$$

We then incorporate this factor into the definition of ξ , which yields a probability density distribution that scales to the outer node of the canonical model:

$$\xi = x \cdot \sigma \cdot f_\sigma$$

Depicted graphically, for selected values of n :

6.3.4 Correspondence To Canonical Quantum Solution

Using the non-dimensional displacement $\xi = x\sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{mK}}{\hbar}}$, we have (with $A_3 = 1/0.327382$ and $H_n(x)$ being the Hermite polynomials):

PKM

$$P_{mp}(\xi) = A_{mp} \cdot \frac{\cos^2\left[\pi\xi\sqrt{\frac{q}{\xi}-\xi^2}\right]}{\sqrt{\frac{q}{\xi}-\xi^2}}$$

CQM

$$|\Psi_n(\xi)|^2 = \left(\frac{H_n(\xi)e^{-\frac{\xi^2}{2}}}{\sqrt{2^n \times n! \sqrt{\pi}}}\right)^2$$

6.3.5 Mathematical Similarity to Canonical Quantum Solution

There is a degree of mathematical similarity between the analytical description of the system in this model and in the canonical model.

The series expansion of this description is of the order:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos^2\left(\pi\xi\Xi\sqrt{\frac{q}{\Xi}-\xi^2}-\phi_{n+1}\right) &\simeq \cos^2(\xi^2) \\ \cos^2(\xi^2) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \cdot \frac{(\xi^2)^{2k}}{(2k)!} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\xi)^k \cdot \frac{(-\xi^2)^k}{(2k)!} \end{aligned}$$

The series expansion of the canonical description is of the order (with normalization constants A_n and Hermite polynomials $\mathcal{H}_n(\xi)$):

$$\phi_n(\xi) = A_n \mathcal{H}_n(\xi) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\xi^2)^k}{k!}$$

6.4 Non-Radiation of Charged Particle in Accelerated Motion

In the case that a material body is a charged particle (e.g., electron), it would be expected that this accelerating particle would radiate energy. But work by H. Puthoff [7] suggests otherwise for such systems in a ground state.

Conclusions

The approach presented in this paper illustrates an alternative way to produce a quantum description of mechanics which closely parallels the canonical description, yet makes no use of the de Broglie matter-wave hypothesis (and its mathematical representation as a wave-function) upon which that canonical description is based.

In addition, the approach suggests that the quantum properties of light (invariant action) impose constraints on the kinematic description of mechanics in phase space (characterized by spatio-temporal probability density distributions and discrete spectra of constants of the motion) in a way analogous to that in which the invariant velocity of light in configuration space imposes constraints on the kinematic description of mechanics in configuration space (characterized by relativistic phenomena, such as Lorentz contraction and time dilation). Viewed another way, just as Special Relativity revealed that the invariant velocity of light in all inertial reference frames imposed constraints on concurrent measurement of position and time in configuration space, so too the invariant action of light in all inertial reference frames imposes constraints on concurrent measurement of 4-position and 4-momentum. The invariant velocity of light means a signal conveying information about time can be received in any inertial reference frame (i.e. there are

no inertial reference frames where the signal's velocity is zero, and thus could not propagate eventually from a point of origin to a point of receipt). Similarly, the invariant action of light means a signal conveying information about momentum can be received in any inertial reference frame (i.e. there are no inertial reference frames where the signal's momentum – and thus action – is zero, and thus could not propagate eventually from a point of origin to a point of receipt).

Further Investigation

Further scrutiny of certain aspects of this model is warranted:

1. What does a fully relativistic phase space kinematics look like in this model?
2. What is the physical significance of the characteristic extrema in the phase space plot of $P_m(x)$ for all potentials?
3. Do the momentum-like segments of $P_m(x)$ indicate probability density of measurability *beyond* the classical turning points represented by the characteristic extrema, and what is the probability density of presence in these classically forbidden regions? Does zero momentum at these boundaries account for zero measurability, or is that merely coincidence?
4. Does the clock synchronization process actually define a vector field in phase space that specifies not only a scalar probability density of measurability but also a probability of measured antiparallel directions (arising from the alternating direction of the electric/magnetic field of an electromagnetic wave at a point in space), and could this vector field be the origin of, or related to, intrinsic spin (i.e. probability of establishing one direction or its opposite for $s = \pm \frac{1}{2}$, or no direction at all at the node where $E = B = 0$ for $s = 0$)? That is, without operationally defining a reference direction, how can a consistent, persistent sense of orientation, for the measurement of directional quantities, be defined among reference frames?
5. Can the Pauli exclusion principle arise from this model in any natural way, rather than being the seemingly bolted-on postulate in the canonical model?
6. How does the scalar field of this model manifest in a general relativistic space-time?

Also, there are other systems to which the method developed above can be applied and the results compared with those of the canonical model. These systems include:

1. Central potential $\left(\frac{1}{r}\right)$ system (e.g. hydrogenic atom)
2. Unbound systems (a refinement of this model – to include complex phase for multi-path systems – might be required for these systems):
 - a. Potential Barrier Problems (simple step potential, rectangular wall, rectangular well)
 - b. Two-slit experiment
3. Yukawa potential
4. Ellipsoidal mass distribution potential (e.g., alpha and beta particles while they are in close proximity to their emitting/absorbing nucleus)

5. Disk mass distribution potential

In addition, this model can be examined in the context of variations of the canonical (wave-function based) model:

1. Copenhagen Interpretation
2. Pilot-Wave (e.g. de Broglie/Bohm)
3. Wigner phase-space formulation

Also, how does this model relate to the long-standing problems associated with the canonical views:

1. Wave-function collapse?
2. Measurement Problem?
3. Classical Limit Problem?

Appendices

A - Notational Simplification - Phase Angle

Given that various discussions involve the use of $\cos(\)$ and $\sin(\)$ conditioned upon the parity of an integer (typically, a spectral index), we define the following to make this use more notationally simple.

With the parity $\mathbb{P}(q)$ of an integer q being as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{P}(q) &= \frac{(1+(-1)^q)}{2} \\ &= 1 \text{ for even values of } q \\ &= 0 \text{ for odd values of } q\end{aligned}$$

we define a phase angle that depends on $\mathbb{P}(q)$ as follows:

$$\Phi_q = \mathbb{P}(q) \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}$$

Now, given that:

$$\cos\left(\alpha \pm \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \sin(\alpha)$$

we can reduce the more complex expression:

$$\left(\delta_{\mathbb{P}(q)} - \mathbb{P}(q)\right) \cdot \cos^n(\alpha) + \mathbb{P}(q) \cdot \sin^n(\alpha)$$

to:

$$\cos^n\left(\alpha - \Phi_q\right)$$

B - Notational Convention

We indicate the domain of evaluation of a function using a notation similar to the notation for the range of evaluation of an integral, typically applied to expressions in square brackets, with the lower bound lb to the lower right of the brackets and the upper bound ub to the upper right, as follows:

$$F(x) = []_{lb}^{ub}$$

This approach is equivalent to expressing the domain of evaluation of the function as follows:

$$lb \leq x \leq ub$$

C - Illustrated Pm Extrema

In the following, using $n = 2$ as an example (though the results are the same for any integral value of n), plot (a) shows the extrema for P_m at $\alpha = 0 + \alpha_e$, $\pi - \alpha_e$ for n (blue) and for $n + 1$, while plot (b) shows the variation of P_m between its extrema for values between (inclusive) n and $n + 1$, $n + 0.1$, $n + 0.2$, ..., $n + 0.8$, $n + 0.9$, $n + 1$. Plot (b) contains plot (a).

$$s = 1, V(x) = Kx^1, \alpha_e = \arccos\left(\frac{2}{3}\right):$$

(a)

(b)

$$s = 2, V(x) = Kx^2, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{4}:$$

(a)

(b)

$$s = -1, V(x) = Kx^{-1}, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{3}:$$

(a)

(b)

$$s = -2, V(x) = Kx^{-2}, \alpha_e = \frac{\pi}{2}:$$

(a)

(b)

References

[1] - A. Einstein, “On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies” - *Annalen der Physik*. **17** (10): 891–921

[2] - Ibid [1], §1

[3] - Max Born, Nobel lecture, 11 December 1954 - “... an idea of Einstein’s ... [made] the duality of particles - light quanta or photons - and waves comprehensible by interpreting the square of the optical wave amplitudes as probability density for the occurrence of photons”

[4] - Richard L. Liboff (Cornell), “Introductory Quantum Mechanics”, Holden-Day, Inc, © 1980

[5] - Ibid [1], p.3 (§1)

[6] - *Am. J. Phys.* 67, 776–782 (1999),

<https://www.reed.edu/physics/faculty/wheeler/documents/Quantum%20Mechanics/Miscellaneous%20Essays/Quantum%20Bouncer/E2.%20Bouncer.pdf>

[7] - H.E. Puthoff, “Quantum Ground States as Equilibrium Particle-Vacuum Interaction States” -

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1204.1952>

[8] - As of 31May2025, it appears that the premise of this paper — that a light signal consisting of an ensemble of identically prepared photons (monochromatic, phase-coherent, polarization type [i.e. of the same eccentricity, orientation and chirality]) exhibits longitudinal sinusoidal

photon detection probability density propagating in free space — is false. If so, then neither is there a self-contradictory definition of synchronism in configuration space (at least not for this reason), nor does the scalar field of measurability in phase space arise from this falsely-presumed behavior of light (i.e. it is not operationally defined this way, or at least not precisely in this way). There may be either other forms of light-signaling that do give rise to the contradiction cited above (and thus to the scalar field in phase space), or other physically-based motivations for asserting the existence of such a scalar field of measurability in phase space. If so, the rest of this paper and derivative papers (e.g. application of the consequences and methods of this paper to 3D systems, such as a $\frac{K}{r}$ central potential system — e.g., hydrogenic atom) still stand as valid explorations of the consequences of such a scalar field in phase space.